

The Third Generation National Curriculum (Georgia), ICT in Teaching and the Formation of 21-st Century Skills in Students

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Abstract:- Nowadays, all developed countries are implementing important changes in the education system, such as the introduction of digital technologies in all subjects. Possession of information and communication technologies, on the other hand, implies the knowledge of electronic tools, the usage will give the student the necessary skills of the 21st century, such as information, media and technological skills, information acquisition and analysis, creativity, critical thinking and problem-solving, communication skills, habits, etc.

As part of the current reforms in Georgia, ICT was included as a compulsory subject in the national curriculum, moreover, based on the needs identified during the Covid pandemic, it was added as a obligatory subject in the second, third, and fourth grade of primary school from January 2021.

All fields, all professions, and all subjects of the 21-st century require these skills, such as the possession of Technologies of the 21st century, thus their usage in the educational process is vital for future success.

By observing and analyzing the importance of the usage of ICT and digital resources in the educational process in Aspindza public school of the Samtskhe-Javakheti region in the second grade of the public school, to improve the skills of reading and understanding the text, it was revealed that the students due to their age (they do not know how to read aloud), it is difficult for them to recognize informative text compared with creative text.

Through the research studies on students' needs and the conducted interventions, it became possible to improve the academic results of students using digital resources.

Keywords:- Digital Resource, Electronic Tool, Technological Skills, Creativity, Critical Thinking.

I. INTRODUCTION

The recently ended world pandemic has reflected the importance of informational technologies and increased its role through the learning process. The educational institutions for both of higher educational institutes and also

schools went through the using of online methods in preparing of learning materials. Therefore, utilizing of online methods through the learning process became obligation rather than necessity.

Today, all developed countries are implementing important changes in the education system, such as the introduction of digital technologies in all subjects. Possession of ICT, on the other hand, implies the knowledge of electronic tools, the usage of which will give the student the skills of the XXI century, such as information, media and technological skills, information acquisition and analysis, creativity, critical thinking and problem-solving. Also communication skills and relevant habits.

Allen (1997) considered the use of technology will be a key factor of the future. Study guides can no longer meet the needs of a rapidly developing world of information explosions. He believed that traditional student-centered approaches and methods could no longer be an effective system that would prepare the new generation to face new challenges in the future.

Based on the testing, it became clear that most of the students had difficulty understanding both the fiction text and the informational text at the beginning of the study. Schematically, this indicator was illustrated:

Fig 1 The beginning of study

This identifies that in a class of 28 students, only a few managed to get six out of ten correct answers.

After reading the creative text, those students who read fluently and well managed it, while the rest showed below-average results.

After reading the informative text, it became obvious that the students had more difficulty here compared to the creative text.

➤ *The Results of the Diagnostic Testing Analysis are as Follows:*

- The maximum score of the information test is 10.
- One correct answer is worth of 1 point. 7 students scored the maximum 10 points, 13 students got 6 points, and 10 students got 5 points. 12 points 14%, 6 points - 57%, 5 points -29%.
- As for the knowledge of the creative text, the test results are as follows:
- The maximum score of the test is 10. 6 points-21%, 4 points-43%, and 3 points-36%.
- It illustrates that the test results are acceptable.
- To determine the role of the use of technology in teaching, several interventions were planned.

As part of the student survey, an anonymous survey was conducted among the students, where 100% of the surveyed students indicated that it is more interesting in the teaching process when the teacher uses digital resources, 78% marked the answer that they understand the text better when they watch a video or a movie, 22% marked the missed question Knowledge.

As a result of an anonymous survey conducted with parents, it was revealed that 89% of them think that their child learns and achieves the goal when the teacher offers additional resources, or he looks for and offers them to his child, for example, when he learns a story or a fable, similar to which there is a movie or cartoon, parents watch it, and after that, the students have no more difficulty in understanding and conveying the information, they remember it for a long time.

The same was revealed based on the teachers' survey: when using digital resources in the lesson - under the issue and purpose, the lesson turns out to be very active, and all students are motivated and involved.

Searching for resources requires additional time and energy from the teacher, but in return, class time is saved and the lesson is productive.

Repeated testing and analysis were performed, which aimed to determine the role of using digital resources in understanding the text. Artistic text "Dragonfly and Ant" and informative text "Bat" were used.

In the process of explaining the artistic text, the students were shown PowerPoint animations arranged according to the text, and the students happily read the fragmented texts that were attached to the pictures.

Later, the students in groups got acquainted with the previously prepared material - colorful pictures of a dragonfly and an ant, and some pictures were also provided for the background.

The students already had the experience and knowledge of creating a comic book in a Word file. In groups, they arranged comics according to episodes.

In advance, using the "chain of events", four episodes were outlined in the reading process, and each group created one episode.

Then the groups made a presentation.

The students talked about why they chose a particular picture, how they wrote down what the cartoon character had to say, etc.

Fig 2 The Study Results

During the presentation, it was revealed that it was easier for the students to work on the task by using a familiar animated resource.

Then the students were given "Dragonfly and Ant" tests, there were ten questions according to the text. Each question was worth one point. 28 students participated in the testing process.

None of the students had to work on the test.

Moreover, they managed to complete the task in a short time (compared to the time spent on the previous test).

➤ *The Results Obtained When Using Digital Resources Were Distributed As Follows:*

- 58%; Sixteen students got – Ten points;
- 23%; Nine points – Seven students;
- 10%; Three students got - Eight points;
- 9%; Two students got – Seven points;

During the explanation of the informative text "Bat", the teacher distributed the printed texts to the students, while reading the text according to the paragraphs, the teacher offered a small video film in parallel mode, where the relevant information of the text was conveyed with colorful pictures and animation. After processing the text,

the students created a living environment for bats and made presentations using the Minecraft game program and using what they learned. The teacher helped and gave hints when necessary. After working on the materials, the students completed the tests, and the obtained results look like this:

➤ *The Analysis of Information Text Testing Data Showed that:*

- 58%; sixteen students got 10 points;
- 23%; nine points - seven students;
- 10%; eight points - three students;
- 9% seven points - two students;

The analysis of the obtained data revealed the importance of digital resources in the teaching of the Georgian language and literature, that had a positive impact on the academic results achieved by the students.

II. CONCLUSION

Overall, according to the results of prior research undoubtedly represent the improvement of motivation of the pupils and also an increase of the academic achievements, that is relevant to the using of informational technologies in learning process. Furthermore, preparing learning materials with technologies reflects its drastic role.

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